

CRUSTAL THICKNESS VARIATIONS UNDER SCHRÖDINGER-SCALE IMPACT BASINS

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Introduction: During large impact events, the crust is thinned and mantle material is uplifted below the centre of the crater, generating a distinctive gravity signature [1]. The amount and horizontal extent of those central uplifts depend upon not only the impact conditions, but also the thermal state at the time of formation [2], the strength behaviour of the target rock, and the physical processes of gravity-driven crater collapse, all of which are areas of ongoing research. On Earth, only a handful of those large craters have been preserved, and observations are limited by the state of erosion. The subsurface structure of craters of that size is, therefore, not well-constrained.

Under lunar gravity, the onset diameter for the uplift of mantle material is ~ 200 km [3]. More than 70 craters in this size range have been identified [4, 5], making the Moon an excellent target for the study of large impact processes. Numerical impact models are often the most suitable method to investigate the formation of complex craters. However, they rely on geophysical observations for benchmarking and validation. Crustal thickness maps are often used to compare simulation results (e.g., [6]) and to derive impact scaling laws (e.g., [2, 7]). While GRAIL crustal thickness maps [8] have greatly enhanced our understanding of the crustal thickness variations introduced by impacts, their spatial resolution could be insufficient to resolve certain aspects of a crater’s subsurface structure.

In this work, we show that the process used to construct the crustal thickness maps can smooth or filter short wavelength variations beneath small to medium sized impact basins. These findings highlight the importance of using the same spatial resolution when comparing numerical impact simulation results with gravity-derived crustal thickness maps.

Methods:

Gravity-derived crustal thickness maps. A new suite of crustal thickness maps was recently derived for the Moon using GRAIL gravity and new seismic analyses of converted phases at the crust-mantle interface [9]. These maps span average crustal thicknesses of 29 to 47 km, reflecting seismic and crust-mantle density contrast uncertainties. Here, we use the map with a global average thickness of 38 km, in agreement with the Apollo body wave travel-time analysis reported in [10]. As with the previous set of GRAIL crustal thickness maps [8], a low-pass filter with a half amplitude at spherical harmonic degree 80 was applied. This filtering was necessary to damp short wavelength gravity signals from the uppermost crust that are unrelated to variations in crust-mantle relief. While the underlying gravity model [11] has a spatial

resolution of 4.5 km at the equator, this filtering process coarsens the resolution by a factor of 10 or more.

Impact simulations. We use iSALE-2D [12-14] to simulate crater formation for a range of impactor diameters ($L=5$ to 95 km). Simulation parameters are based on previous simulations of peak-ring basins under lunar gravity and described in [15]. The resolution is 20 cells per projectile radius (CPPR) with cell sizes between 0.125 and 2.375 km, enabling a much more detailed description of crust-mantle interface relief underneath lunar craters than can be achieved with the gravity-derived crustal thickness maps.

Additionally, we present a simulation of the Schrödinger basin ($L=24$ km, a pre-impact crustal thickness of 32.5 km, CPPR=24), which plays a prominent role in upcoming missions. Notably, the Farside Seismic Suite (2027) will make seismic measurements at a location between Schrödinger’s crater rim and peak ring [16].

Filtering of iSALE results. To simulate the filtering process involved in constructing the GRAIL-derived maps, we project the iSALE simulated crust-mantle interfaces onto a global lunar grid. We then express this in spherical harmonics and apply the same filter [17] to the spherical harmonic coefficients that was used in the gravity studies. This ensures that the results from our impact simulations will have the same effective spatial resolution as the gravity-derived crustal thickness maps.

Results and Discussion:

Effect of the filter.

Figure 1: Simulated surface topography (blue), crust-mantle interface (blue), and filtered crust-mantle interface (magenta) for a subset of impactor sizes (10, 16, 23.75, 30.4, 40 and 47.5 km). Horizontal profiles are normalised by the final rim-to-rim radius of the simulated crater.

Simulated craters range in diameter from 80 km ($L=5$ km) to 1,100 km ($L=95$ km) providing a good sample of lunar craters in the relevant size-range. No mantle material is uplifted for the smallest crater, whereas nearly the entire crust is removed for the largest craters. The filtered crust-mantle interfaces (**Fig. 1**) show how the simulated subsurface would appear in the GRAIL crustal thickness maps. Both the size and shape of the mantle uplifts are significantly altered. This effect is most pronounced for craters less than 400 to 450 km in diameter. Small mantle uplifts are removed entirely by the filter (**Fig. 1a**). While the overall shape and position of notable features, such as the annulus of thickened crust, are largely preserved for craters >450 km in size (**Fig. 1e, f**), the profile is still smoothed. Even for the largest craters, the crustal annulus is shallower and somewhat wider in the filtered version than in the unfiltered simulation results.

Figure 2: Relative change in percent of central uplift metrics caused by filtering for simulated lunar craters (black squares) and Schrödinger (red S). (a) Relative difference in amplitude of the mantle uplift, measured with respect to the pre-impact crust-mantle interface. (b) Relative difference in the position of the annulus of thickened crust (deepest point), measured from the crater centre.

No characteristic feature of the crust-mantle interface is consistently preserved during the filtering process for craters smaller than about 450 km. In particular, the amplitude of the mantle uplift (**Fig. 2a**) and the position of the annulus of thickened crust (**Fig. 2b**) change significantly. For impact basins less than 450 km in diameter, the gravity-derived crustal thickness maps might misrepresent the true subsurface structures of these basins. For a ~ 300 km simulated crater, for example, the filter moves the annulus of thickened crust outwards by 22.5 km (~ 0.15 crater radii).

Schrödinger basin. This peak-ring basin (~ 330 km) is an example of a lunar crater, where the subsurface might be incorrectly portrayed by the gravity-derived crustal thickness maps. The full resolution unfiltered simulated crust-mantle interface does not appear to be a good fit to the observational data (**Fig. 3a**). However, after applying the same filter as used in the gravity studies, the crustal thickness map and simulation results compare favourably. In particular, the post-filter crustal thickness profile (**Fig. 3b**) closely fits the observational data. Most notably, the filter changes the position (**Fig. 2b**) and depth of the crustal annulus. Crust beneath the inner edge of the peak ring and the crater rim might be up to 10 km thicker than estimated by the gravity-derived crustal

thickness maps. Remaining discrepancies between the filtered profile and the GRAIL data might be a product of post-impact modification or the neglect of lateral variations in crustal density in the gravity-derived maps. Finally, we note that Schrödinger was likely formed by an oblique impact [18] in a heterogeneous target (as visible in the wide uncertainty bands), which cannot be accounted for in our axisymmetric impact simulations.

Figure 3: (a) Simulated surface and crust-mantle interface (blue) and filtered crust-mantle interface (magenta). (b) Unfiltered (blue) and filtered (magenta) simulated crustal thickness for the Schrödinger basin. Black lines are azimuthally averaged profiles and $1\text{-}\sigma$ uncertainties based on LOLA topography and GRAIL crustal thickness data.

Our selected simulation parameters produce a reasonable fit with observations after filtering the results. However, the true subsurface structures below the crater remain ambiguous, particularly below the peak ring. Seismic data collected by the Farside Seismic Suite could provide important additional constraints on the crustal thickness signatures of impact basins.

Conclusions: When comparing impact simulations with GRAIL-derived crustal thickness maps, care must be taken to compare the results using the same filtering approach and spatial resolution. This is particularly relevant for impact basins with diameters less than about 450 km. We show that filtered iSALE simulations of the Schrödinger basin compare favourably with the crustal thickness maps.

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